

THE CULTURE OF READING IN THE CURRENT UZBEK FAMILY: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Annotation: This article analyzes the culture of reading in the Uzbek family, which is one of the most pressing problems today. In the article, the author pointed out that only reading, that is, enlightenment, can save humanity from various material and spiritual threats. According to the author, it is true that the low level of reading culture in Uzbek families is influenced by various threats (Internet, market economy, ideological threats, etc.) as well as internal problems in the spiritual environment of families.

Key words: Uzbek people, reading, culture of reading, humanity, reading, listening, Internet, market economy, ideological threats, spiritual gap.

In the Uzbek family, love for books from time immemorial, preservation of existing books as eyebrows, reading is considered one of the long-standing traditions and has finally gained importance in the original spiritual maturation of our glue.

Elim azal has long been a book-loving quality. Genuine book-loving is, in fact, a human quality that drinks water from the library, which, consequently, reflects the level of spiritual perfection of a person. And in our great people, this quality was formed in the atmosphere of the family, at first it was formed in the form of interesting listening, hearing the tales of the grandparents who sang the folk stories in various family circles, weddings, feasts, banquets, Gossip. Therefore, listening-was becoming the original condition for the perception, understanding and mastering of what was read. In turn, listening necessitated the centralization of all attention, that is, the concentration on a single point, and as a result, a harmonious combination of reading and reading occurred in human activity, consisting of a complex process that leads it towards spiritual perfection. And the basis of the reading was the same reading and hard work.

American psychologist scientists R. Karnikau and F. Makeelrou conducted special scientific research on the issue of reading and uqish. In their opinion, the natural physiological-psychological capabilities of the individual, which allow me to preserve the knowledge acquired in certain forms at different levels. That is, the person: 10 percent when he reads the source himself; 20 percent when he hears the information from other people; 30 percent when he sees the event, events and processes that happened; 50 percent when he sees the event, events and processes that happened and hears the information about them; 80 percent of the data itself when it is transmitted (spoken, demonstrated) to other people; it turns out that it will be able to keep up to 90 percent of the data in mind when reading and reading and applying the acquired knowledge (data, information)to its activities.

In Japan, 25 books per person are read annually. The Swiss read an average of 10 books a year, while the French read 7. Scientists estimate that individuals spend 3.5 – 4 hours of their time every day watching television (more specifically, watching). The time spent on the

internet, the "web of the spider", is even more. But the reading is only about 2.5 minutes apart. 14% of all residents in Japan, 12% in America, and 11% in England and France regularly read books. There are 1 book per 6 people if in Turkey¹.

I think we should be aware of the real situation in them and be able to draw conclusions about the situation in ourselves. Because, although the role of each people in the overall scale of development is also measured by the number of books that those people read. In the opinion of the Great Writer Vidiadhar Naipaul, who won the Nobel Prize in literature in 2002, "what kind of nation is determined not by the greatness of his ancestors who lived in the past, but by his standing-life today, including his literature".

We call the book oftob. This is what our ancestors say from time immemorial. And the computer can't say that. Without a flashlight, the computer will absolutely not work. Where the sun does not fall, the crop also does not end and becomes porous. The brains of people who have not read books are also hollowed out. That is why such a head is usually compared to a pumpkin. Because, although the inside of the pumpkin will also be empty"².

When you see the excessive intensity of the flow of information, like a flood, a tsunami, you both admire and burn, the one you catch. In this bejilov process, there is enough anxiety and risk, as well as benefit. The "saint of the Saints" Lord Alisher Navoi in the time of his life said that only one person's brain can receive in 60 years the volume of information that today's 21st Century person has only 2 (two!) is taking day by day...

Why is the spiritual state of the whole world getting poorer as information gets richer? After all, is information not the basis for science? When we look logically, science should also increase as the volume of information increases! Why is continuous information making human souls even tougher, turning into a giant charsang yo metin millstone?

In this matter, our great ancestors were already confused. Seven hundred years ago, our grandfather Revgari, one of the seven pirs, said: "information will be retail, it is not true science." In the case of Sheikh Shibli, they say: "I read four thousand hadiths, I memorized four faces, of which I followed four and reached my goal."³.

So, all the main talk is that the swims are received continuously in the processing of information in the human brain and thinking. Unnecessary Stone is a burden of trouble to the head, than, while processed information. Be aware that there is much more harm than the benefit of such a load.

Experts note, that the next paytd hlard also observed a decrease in memory. If representatives of the luminous generation complain about the decrease in the memory of our grandparents, we will see that this is a matter of course. Because, as a person's UI continues to pass, memory becomes more hot due to the fact that oxygen does not ferment the brain in the achar micdor. Such a negative and alarming region is also observed in the NIM cause?

Experts who study the tissues of the human brain scientifically point out that the main cause of pain, memory loss isī, excessive Zied exhaustion, and the brain is overflowing with non-specific messages. Constantly working betinim without a steep agenda, days off and not eating properly, all this indicates a negative impact on the functioning of the nervous system, and, above all, on memory. Most scholars agree that, by opinion, television also has a negative

¹ "Китоб дунёси" газетаси. 2013 йил 10 июль.

² "Оила даврасида" газетаси. 2016 йилнинг 21 январь.

³ Бу ҳақда қаранг: Исоқов Б. Р. Оила – жамиятнинг юраги. – Наманган, 2018. – Б. 355.

impact on memory. Am I really like that? If you watch all the shows during the day without leaving the televisor, of course, there is also a negative impact on memory, some doctors say. However, popular science, history, not watching ziei shows and quizzes, and due to viewing, memory improves a lot. To think, to think, maurburla gives a great support in sharpening memory. In one decision with viewing interesting shows, badiy is useful in the idea of reading books, crossword puzzles, skanvord puzzles and puzzles, playing chess, oral counting and learning a language, all of which bring uta Good and necessary information and make memory more resilient.

In 1998, the average number of queries in "Google" was 9.8 thousand, which now (in 2018) exceeds even 5.5 trillion. Now we are observing the "Google" – effect, that is, we got on the "Nina", which is as pleasant as receiving information in any amount with extreme speed. This, in turn, leads to the fact that our memory, albeit slowly, still decreases. Our working memory is also shrinking more and more, year after year, day after day. In 2011, an interesting paper was published in the journal "Science" about an experiment in which a young man was killed in a car accident. According to the same article, students who can access the internet very quickly and easily, and students keep information in mind 100 times less than students of the pre-computer era. If it is the same that since then our brain has changed. And we prefer to store the information that must be stored in our original memory in computer memory. Our addiction to computers is becoming more and more intense. The number of people who correctly calculate information in it is also increasing. Who can guarantee that this information is correct? If we turn over our discretion to Internet technologies in full, we will continue to lose our "I" as a person in a monand way.

Of course, knowledge begins with information. However, ignorance also begins with information that benefits someone. That is, information that does not lead a person towards thinking leads to ignorance and deceives and deceives people. Therefore, any person is obliged to teach himself to process information. If not, then the breathless vortex of information will devour him alive. He will guide every hour to every status. So who or what teaches us how to process existing information? Surely Mutala! The reading of good books does not oblige us to read Life and nature, to read, understand, know man and The Creator, to follow his correct, Noble instructions, stimulates through propaganda and encouragement, fills and teaches us pleasure...

As for the problem of truly reading books, this is now a whole other matter. Especially if you have the works of Stevenson, Defoe, Gogol or Chekhov in your hands, such an activity is a wonderful and unusual activity of an immodest degree, which will always give pleasure, pleasure and tranquility in any conditions – both at industrialization trips and at lunchtime, when the price of the precious paper falls, even in the years of sleepiness, depression and confusion, and even on an empty stomach.

So what is real recitation itself? This is an allanechuk thing that always gives an elegant answer to those shifts in which the eye in US, which is subtly in harmony with humanity in man, is not progressing. While the eye is not progressing, we are separated from butterflies as well as elephants. To another, recitation gives a person shodu sensitivity...

...Recitation is about insisting on divine primitiveness, because we create and become creative when we are obsessed with reading. Finally, Mutola therefore shows us such a positive effect that, seeing how bright and sublime a person with two ears and two legs like ourselves can climb, we also envy them to the fullest, sincerely envious and incomparably...

Recitation is also a mental work that keeps people full, because you will also be faced with various opinions that regularly offend a person in the Mutola circuit. They stir up your mind and cause you to suffer so much that even, if not for one, one would say, "was it better for me to be uneducated than to go through this ordeal?"... Here is such a word, which, by the grace of Vissarion Grigorievich Belinsky, also (1811 – 1843) soothes thinking people: "keep in a hurry, still we will have cast-iron roads, air mail, still we will have factories, manufakturas will reach maturity, and folk wealth will increase even more, but religious feelings will intensify, here is where the original matter itself! We will be carpenters, we will be locksmiths, we can also be factory workers, however, we can truly be real people – here's what the most basic issue is!"

In fact, this is a really cool issue, very broad even when it is a matter, an issue that does not entail a positive response, perhaps because it does not have a complete answer that satisfies everyone equally... It seems that humanity has not become so worse over time, but even though it has not become even better!..

When everyone reads books, it is not really a normative phenomenon. Not everyone can be read. Not everyone can be readers, just as not everyone can be an excellent specialist in eyeliner, Medicine Man, artist, forecaster, entrepreneur, selfless, inventor, singer, collector or white ants. A passion for reading in a unique way, a reading talent is not available to everyone, so it is much more common in nature than a tendency to steal, but much less often than a passion for drinking rosa and having a good snack. In the case of Boz, my readers say that I will be a much more plentiful creature, the happiness of mankind to communicate with the best and greatest people of reason than to prolong his life, to have a higher opinion of himself, than to extend his life more than anything else. On the other hand, the reader is a kind of Shaddad and a fearless creature, because communication with the best minds of mankind through books can lead to such suffering discoveries that about these discoveries, Eccléziast said: "the abundance of knowledge also increases grief." That's why you sometimes get carried away by the thought that" come on, Aries now is that book, which I prefer to be an expert on white ants".⁴

You are also well aware that the order "on the development of the printing and distribution system of book products, the establishment of a commission on book reading and the promotion of reading culture", signed by the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev on January 12, 2017, is one of the most important documents in this regard. After the adoption of this order, the attitude towards the book among the population, especially among the younger generation, has changed radically in a positive way, making sure that the original flower of thought is of particular importance in human maturation.

As you know, art is one of the main purifiers of our consciousness and leads to spiritual and educational perfection. Through it you can find the way to the hearts, thoughts of all people. But are we always able to make the right use of these tabarruk field opportunities? Or is the image of the heroes of our time being created in our social life, whom we look at with enthusiasm, who can become an example for everyone? In our opinion, on the screens, it is difficult for us to focus all our attention on important human aspects in this idea, both in songs and in scenes, and in literature.

⁴ "Тафаккур" журнали. – 2001. – №2. – Б. 59–72.

Books worth the treatment can also be chosen by everyone based on their taste, level. The important thing is to comply with the main requirement in bibliotherapy, that is, the work should be interesting, the process of reading should not only give pleasure, but also encourage thinking, forcing a sick person to think. It is also advisable for the main character of the work to be in a situation that has happened in your life at some point and is still stealing your rest. It is also necessary that the book being read gives a person a calm and uplifting mood, instills firm confidence in the solution of existing problems as though they were at heart, and leaves a vivid impression on people.

What books give strength, first of all, to the mind and heart during reading? Examples of classical literature in the first gala! The narrative style in one episode evokes stagnant and stable emotions in people even from their own sleep. The hero of the work also encourages you to think about the mistakes you made. The reading of classical works serves as a kind of treatment when people suffer mental shocks and when the central nervous system is disturbed, in a state of neurosis and in situations where it is difficult to forget rather unpleasant memories. Detective and adventure works instill the virtue of attention, diligence and observation. In the case of complex plots, mahzun is also much more distracting from fantasies and worries. Various unpleasant thoughts are firmly entrenched in the brain, and when a person is mentally compressed, reading a book is leisurely, truly undergoing the function of medical treatment. Science fiction works, on the other hand, expand the perception of things that are likely to happen, to happen in the future, to make thoughts and desires unabashedly delusional, to admit that there may be such an opinion and desire as I am with others. This type of book is usually recommended as a medicine for people who suffer from fear and panic, living in strict order.

In the case of a strict rhythm in Nazi (poetic) works, it brings to the norm the processes taking place in the body, raises the mood, instills confidence in a person in his strength. The depressive state is also used in the treatment of stuttering after a stroke. Various fairy tales and folklore literature are used to the rules and observances of being treated without difficulty. These types of books are very hasty, disobedient, unspoken and have much more hands on raising "earless" children and give the expected effect from the very beginning.

Legal literature, on the other hand, teaches to prevent various alarming situations and enter into treatment without conflict. Helps adolescents during their transition to boyhood, raises the mood after surgical procedures. Philosophical and religious literature gives people an idea of the integrity of the world, the place of man in it and its role. Acute mental shocks also provide much relief from chronic mental distress. The diverse information extracted from the book forms a new connection between the part of our brain that is responsible for short and long-term memory and makes our brain more genuine.

Any person, first of all, finds his place only in a family where my parents read books and only have a rural, non-neighborhood, true worldview, if he does not find a place in the family – it is difficult to find a place in society at a decent level; it is unlikely that he will find his dignity in the family, if he The family is closely connected to the motherland by such spiritual bonds and becomes a homeland within the Motherland for every person. The concepts of family and homeland are intertwined precisely at this point. As a result of this, the family member becomes a part of the homeland and a citizen. When families are Society, members are people, people, in turn, they will continue to become the people of a whole country.

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